

ABOUT MUSIC CULTURE AND THE ART OF CONDUCTING**Sofya Tajetdinova**

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Abstract. *This article talks about the subject of musical culture and the history and theory of the art of conducting, musical works of conductors.*

Keywords: *music, theory, subject, conductor, art, orchestra.*

О МУЗЫКАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ И ИСКУССТВЕ ДИРИЖИРОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье говорится о предмете музыкальной культуры, истории и теории искусства дирижирования, музыкальных произведениях дирижеров.*

Ключевые слова: *музыка, теория, предмет, дирижер, искусство, оркестр.*

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", based on the principles of democratization, individualization of education, consideration of regional characteristics, all educational subjects, including music Concept of teaching was developed.

The educational subject of musical culture serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to implement the education of national pride and patriotism, to develop skill, sophistication, artistic taste, to expand the range of thought, to educate independence and initiative.

The subject of musical culture is connected with all subjects taught in secondary general education schools, including literature, fine arts, physical education, work and other subjects. The introduction of the state educational standard in musical education, as well as in all academic subjects, allows full use of national musical heritage. These are reflected in popular folk tunes and songs, creative activities of singers and musicians, status, shashmaqom, epics, and today's modern musical activity. Such opportunities of musical art serve as a unique unique resource in educating the new generation and in their development. The new educational content of music education based on the state educational standards ensures the development of students' musical knowledge and skills, as well as observation, memory strengthening, visual imagination, creativity, independence, initiative, artistic and musical taste. For the musical-aesthetic development of students, the teacher should prepare seriously in his work and ensure that the lessons are held at a high methodical level.

After all, the lesson requires the teacher to have a lot of willpower, research, responsiveness, and quick reaction to various pedagogical situations. Ineffective lesson

deficiencies do not give the teacher peace and happiness for a long time, he feels the need to look back and search for the reasons. The lesson of music culture is the main form of organizing music education at school. Although music clubs and optional classes are in practice, the lesson never loses its importance, because the lesson of music culture includes various forms of musical activity. These are group singing, performing musical rhythmic movements, listening to music, musical literacy, musical creativity, students playing musical instruments, etc.

The lesson is the leading factor in the system of music education, because it covers all students. One of the important features of the music lesson is that it is distinguished by the fact that it arouses more creative pleasure, sensual feelings and imaginative experiences. Music, especially, has a positive effect on the development of students from the intellectual and moral aesthetic point of view. Music lesson is different from other subjects with its unique features: First, music lesson, music history, theory, various examples of instrument performance, choral training, music literacy, listening to music, analysis of musical works, student instrument It consists of such elements as performing on instruments, performing rhythmic movements. Therefore, the music lesson is a mixed lesson type. Secondly, music differs from other forms of art in its means of expression. If fiction is expressed by artistic words, visual arts by colors and graphic lines, dance by artistic movements, music is expressed by means of melody created in musical sounds. If we perceive works of art and sculpture by seeing, fiction by reading and hearing, cinema and theater by seeing and hearing, then we can perceive music only by listening attentively.

Music is an art associated with a precise measure of time. If you tune in to the tempo of the music being performed and listen carefully to every element of it, the piece will not be perfectly understood. That's why we feel its new artistic aspects by listening to classical works again and again. It is difficult to describe the emotions expressed through music. "When words fail, music comes to the rescue." Thirdly, music has an active emotional impact on students, makes them happy, and evokes positive experiences. A good, meaningful and interesting music lesson makes students happy, happy and relaxed.

Even if the music lesson is placed at the end of the lesson, the students will relax and their fatigue will dissipate. Today, the study of the effect of music on the human psyche and physiology through functional music is a new field of music science. The music lesson differs from other subjects in its mixed lesson type (structure), means of expression (language) and active psychological influence.

Therefore, music lessons play an important role in the formation of students' personality and outlook. A special emotional atmosphere is characteristic for a music lesson. This is natural, of course, because music is the language of emotions. Music excites, has a positive effect on the

psyche of students and creates a certain mood. Under the influence of the teacher, the formed artistic impressions are strengthened not only by expressive performance, but also by the art of "words", facial expressions, and various movements.

Pupils' attention is drawn to the playing music and their emotions are developed. Pupils enter the world of musical images and clearly feel expressiveness. Despite the common features, each lesson is unique and unique. It is known that the good organization of the desired work is half its success, and this fully applies to the lesson of music culture. In the lesson, goals and tasks, content, structure, tools and methods should be carefully thought out. Otherwise, no positive results can be achieved in music lessons. Preparation for the lesson depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills and abilities. This provides educational, educational and developmental possibilities of musical material, as well as ways of their application.

In fact, in order to successfully implement the tasks of musical education, it is necessary to study the work in depth. It is appropriate to select the work taking into account the musical preparation of the students and their age characteristics. The interpretation of the lesson content will include various musical works. It is very important to determine the structure of the lesson to ensure their integrity. Because it is important to pay attention to the succession of different musical activities. Thinking about the musical and artistic structure of the lesson, the teacher should preserve the important emotional state of the students and apply methods of attracting their attention to the process of transition from one piece to another. Also, it is necessary to take into account the physical, mental and emotional conditions of students and the uniqueness of the class when creating a lesson plan. For example, in primary grades, young students cannot maintain their attention for a long time. Therefore, it is advisable to change their activities in a timely manner and prevent students' interest from fading. It is effective to teach a complex song and dance during several lessons. After learning complex musical-rhythmic movements, it is not appropriate to move to singing. It is also necessary to take into account the place of the music lesson in the schedule, that is, what time this lesson will be held on that day.

It is also important which lesson is followed by music culture. If music culture classes are held after labor education and especially after physical education class, it is necessary to start with activities that encourage students to think and perceive.

In each specific case, it is very important for the teacher to take into account the peculiarities of the class, students' interest in this or that musical activity, and their level of preparation. Thus, the creative approach of the teacher is required to develop and implement the structure of the lesson, taking into account all the conditions. This helps to make each lesson structure unique. After all, during the period from one training to the next, other subjects may be

passed and the impressions may be shallow. The teacher should be able to maintain overall impressions and interests in the music lesson during the week.

If the content of the music lesson is planned in advance, the methods and tools that have been thought out will find their expression, and the interaction between the teacher and the students should always be carried out on the basis of an interesting process. However, some unforeseen circumstances may occur and advice cannot be given for every specific situation. Sometimes unexpected situations happen during the course of the lesson. The teacher's professional skills require drawing conclusions relevant to each situation without losing oneself. As a result, the goal of the lesson is achieved and implemented in the specified structure. Experienced teachers attach special importance to the overall lesson structure.

Because different elements and stages of the lesson are mutually compatible and related to each other. Based on various methods (comparison of the work (T-schema), problem situation, brainstorming, scarab), the teacher increases the activity of the students through creative tasks and tries to achieve the desired results. It is known that the quality of a modern music lesson is determined by the activity of students. The problem of activity is solved not only by an interesting structure of the lesson, but also by using methods that create interest in students. It often depends on the teacher's individual approach to each student. This is one of the important tasks of a modern teacher. Music meets with the teacher and students once a week. Music class requires a wide range of activities with students. Therefore, the teacher should know his students well, understand their strengths and weaknesses, interests, enter their world and evaluate the possibilities of each student.

It is desirable to try to establish a direct dialogue in the lesson, to use a wide range of tools and methods of exhortation, questioning look, and facial expression to various questions. Each musical activity allows students to have an individual approach. This can be clearly observed when students accompany musical instruments, give creative tasks, etc., when studying two- and three-voice works. Differential tasks arouse interest in students. Successful completion of assigned tasks by students activates their musical development. One of the most specific types in the art of music is conducting

Until recently, it was believed that one cannot study to become a conductor, but one must be born as a conductor, that such ability is given to a person by nature itself. Also, not everyone always understands what "conducting technique" is. There are different ideas about this concept.

Some musicians consider the conducting technique as a means of expressing the essence of the musical image and work through hand movements. This opinion was supported by S. A. Kazachkov, A. P. Ivanov-Radkevich, I. A. Musin. In particular, I. A. Musin wrote: "Hand gestures have become their own language and replaced the conductor's speech. With its help, the conductor

talks to the orchestra and the audience about the content of the music." And some understand the technique of conducting as the methods of managing a choir or orchestra performing a musical piece (M. I. Kanershtein, I. V. Razumnyi). Others understand the concept of conducting technique as the management of a choir or an orchestra performing a musical piece (V. G. Rajnikov, J. M. Debelaya). In our opinion, conducting technique is primarily the interpretation of the music being played by the conductor using his hand movements. The word "conductor" is pronounced differently in different languages: the Germans say "Dirident", the Italians say "Diridente", the French say "Chef orchestre", the English say "Conductor". In any language, this word means leader, chief, director. Thus, the conductor is the leader of the orchestra. Its main task is to control the active and well-organized life of the community.

The conductor ensures that the musicians perform the musical piece in harmony, that they start and end the piece together, play their instruments in unison, keep the pauses in time, and start the tune in unison. The conductor should adapt the performance of the musicians to a single rhythm and tempo, and give signs to direct them to the performance. By the way, for a long time, many people understood that the task of the conductor is only to ensure the performance of the orchestra in a uniform rhythm. In fact, the profession of a conductor is very complicated and difficult. It requires a lot of mental and nervous work, constant physical strength. Therefore, a conductor must have good health and endurance. The self-control necessary for him also depends on the state of health and nervous system. The conductor is the main coordinator of the activities of more than 100 musicians. His role is partly similar to that of a director. The director is the artistic director of the stage work in the theater, he coordinates all the work related to the preparation of the performance.

The conductor can also be considered as the direct director of the orchestra. Leo Tolstoy's "What is Art?" in his famous article called "The activity of art is to restore the once-experienced emotion and express it through words, using movement, paint, sounds, and symbols in such a way that others can also experience this emotion." consists of delivery. Art is a type of human activity, through which a person conveys his feelings to others through external signs, and they transfer this feeling to their hearts. they feel from the heart." This recognition directly applies to the art of conducting. This is the conductor's emotional influence. his ability to convey emotions to others is important. First of all, he needs to captivate the orchestra with his emotions, and then to enchant the audience with him.

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